

Chan, K., Fung, M., Lau, J. & Zhang, J. (2023). A Bootcamp as an experiential learning activity for nurturing creative talent: A Hong Kong case study. In V. Tütlys, L. Vaitkutė & C. Nägele (Eds.), *Vocational Education and Training Transformations for Digital, Sustainable and Socially Fair Future. Proceedings of the 5th Crossing Boundaries Conference in Vocational Education and Training, Kaunas, 25. – 26. May* (pp. 93–106). European Research Network on Vocational Education and Training, VETNET, Vytautas Magnus University Education Academy, Institute of Educational Science. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7808360>

A Bootcamp as an Experiential Learning Activity for Nurturing Creative Talent: A Hong Kong Case Study

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Abstract

A three-day bootcamp in video production was held for 82 secondary school students enrolled in the CLAP-TECH Multimedia Storytelling Applied Learning Course. The bootcamp utilized an experiential learning model to provide students with out of classroom learning. This paper uses a case study approach to explore how the bootcamp enhanced student learning. The learning objectives, activity design, and manpower/resource support are described. Teacher observations and a post-activity survey of students are used to assess results. Altogether 16 short videos were produced. Student representatives explained the ideation and challenges they faced. Survey results and observations demonstrate that the bootcamp benefited students in personal, cognitive, and social dimensions. Among these, personal development and social benefits were particularly notable. Students appreciated for the hands-on content of the bootcamp. Vocational and professional education service providers can consider designing a bootcamp as a tool to develop a specific skill within a short period of time for creativity training.

Keywords

experiential learning, learning outside the classroom, creative industry, creativity education

1 Introduction

Launched in Hong Kong in 2019, CLAP-TECH Pathway is a model of career and life development education beginning in senior secondary school, with an articulation path into a Higher Diploma in ArtTech Design. It aims to provide alternative education pathways that nurture talent for new-collar jobs currently in high demand. As part of the Jockey Club Multiple Pathways Initiative funded by the Hong Kong Jockey Club Charities Trust, CLAP-TECH

Pathway involves tripartite collaboration between three parties, namely Hong Kong Baptist University, industry partners, and secondary schools in Hong Kong. An initial track in Information and Communication Technology was launched in 2019 and a second in Creative Technology and Innovation in 2022. In August 2022, 86 secondary students participated in a three-day bootcamp in video production. Using this bootcamp as a case study, this article demonstrates how a bootcamp model can be used to enhance vocational education in the creative industry among secondary students.

CLAP-TECH Pathway is largely based upon the P-TECH (Pathways in Technology Early College High School) model initiated by IBM in 2011. First launched in the United States, the P-TECH model involves an applied education pathway from high school to an associate degree in information technology, administered in close collaboration with industry. It has been adopted in 28 countries and regions, including Australia, Singapore, South Korea, Taiwan, Thailand, United Kingdom (Litow & Kelley, 2021). CLAP-TECH also draws heavily from CLAP@JC, a 5-year programme empowering Hong Kong youth to navigate their school-to-work journey, promoting career and life development (“CLD”) competence, and providing an environment with supportive enablers and infrastructure. CLAP@JC’s CLD perspective has been blended with P-TECH’s key success factors to produce CLAP-TECH Pathway. CLAP-TECH provides a learning journey filled with skills training as well as self-understanding and goal-setting education to empower young people to be job-ready in the selected industry.

According to industry leaders in Hong Kong, there is currently high demand in the job market for creative talent with strong digital skills (Google & Ipsos, 2019). CLAP-TECH’s Creative Technology and Innovation track was introduced in January 2022 in response to this demand. The program aims to develop students’ competence in storytelling, creativity, the use of technology, and entrepreneurship. It prepares graduates to take up future jobs as content curators, business designers, and creative technologists (Chan et al., 2022). The track starts with an Applied Learning (ApL) course at the senior secondary school level titled Multimedia Storytelling. This is bridged with a self-financed Higher Diploma program offered by the Hong Kong Baptist University (Hong Kong Baptist University, 2022). An important feature of the study pathway is that industry partners support the learning of students throughout the entire journey. They participate in curriculum design and program direction as well as offering mentorships, internships and other workplace experiences. There are currently 12 industry partners collaborating with the program.

CLAP-TECH’s Multimedia Storytelling Applied Learning course has five modules: overview of multimedia storytelling, content creation, multimedia production, creativity and design thinking, and creative project for social good (Chan et al., 2022). The entire course consists of 180 contact hours, with each module requiring between 25 hours and 40 contact hours. The final module is an exercise in project-based learning, requiring students to design a multimedia storytelling piece advocating for a social cause. The teaching and learning mode for the Applied Learning course includes classroom teaching, visits to companies and cultural sites, intensive learning experiences, and guest lectures from industry partners. Mentors recruited from industry partners also meet with groups of students to provide career guidance. To support tripartite collaboration in designing and implementing the program, a Program Management Committee comprised of representatives of secondary schools, industry partners, and the project management team at the Hong Kong Baptist University was formed to lead the curriculum design and the teaching and learning practice. The first cohort of Multimedia Storytelling students in 2022 comprised 120 Form 4 students (equivalent to Grade 10 in the US system) recruited from seven secondary schools.

As part of the program’s coursework, a three-day Innovation Bootcamp in video production was held for the first cohort of Multimedia Storytelling students in August 2022. Bootcamps in the technology industry refer to intensive training courses that teach a specific skill in high

demand in the job market. They usually involve a focused agenda and project-based learning that requires students engage in realistic tasks (Sey & Garrido, 2016; Iron Hack, 2022). While adult education bootcamps are often several-month courses preparing learners directly for the job market, mini-bootcamps used in primary or secondary education are usually designed to expose young people to the realities of the technology industry and to generate interest in related careers (Sey & Garrido, 2016; World Bank, 2018). The Innovation Bootcamp took place after students had completed the first module of the course, Overview of Multimedia Storytelling. Over the course of the bootcamp, students went through the full process of producing a self-directed short video, from brainstorming and creating storylines, to shooting, and finally editing and adding post-production effects. The bootcamp was carried out in a rented facility for media production managed by the Hong Kong Federation of Youth. A total of 82 students participated.

In the remainder of this article, we first explore conceptual frameworks for understanding the mini bootcamp model of intensive experiential learning. We then discuss our research method. Next, we introduce in detail the curriculum design, content, and daily schedule of the bootcamp. Subsequently, we present and discuss the evaluation results and findings from teachers and students. Finally, we provide conclusions and recommendations for both practitioners and researchers.

2 Conceptual framework

2.1 Experiential learning

The bootcamp carried out as part of CLAP-TECH's Multimedia Storytelling course can be understood both in terms of experiential learning and learning outside the classroom. Experiential learning can be variously defined as "learning by doing" (Lewis & Williams, 1994) or "learning through reflection on doing" (Smith, 2016). Keaton and Tate (as cited in Kolb, 2014) characterized experiential learning as a situation where "the learner is directly in touch with the realities being studied [...] rather than merely thinking about the encounter or only considering the possibility of doing something with it" (p. 7). Hands-on experiential learning is a central component of vocational and professional education. By transitioning students from merely thinking about phenomena to actually engaging with them, it fosters the development of contextualized, applied knowledge that prepares students for the workplace.

Experiential learning in vocational education ranges from project-based learning that can be conducted in the classroom to work-based learning such as internships. The tradition of project-based learning traces its roots to Italian architectural and engineering education in the 16th century. Students in these early schools completed challenging design assignments for competitions, mimicking real competitions for commissions (Knoll, 1997). Project-based learning is better known as a component of American progressive education, heavily inspired by Dewey and his theories of experiential learning (Knoll, 1997). Independent projects where students solve practical problems have become a popular component of vocational training. On the one hand, projects allow students to apply the disparate skills that they have learned to a complete piece of work. On the other hand, they help students contextualize their learning, seeing where different pieces of knowledge fit into a larger whole (Knoll, 1997). Projects give room for students to apply their knowledge to creatively solve realistic problems. They are seen as a way to develop student initiative, creativity, and judgement (Knoll, 1997). Internships and other work-based learning experiences are also forms of experiential learning commonly deployed in vocational education. By putting learners in contact with the real world of work, these allow for "authentic learning experiences" and enhance student readiness for the school-to-work transition (Watters, Pillay, & Flynn, 2016). In Europe, the German dual model of vocational education is widely recognized as a successful model of high-quality vocational education. This model combines experiential learning in the workplace and classroom-based

education (Euler, 2013; Leney & Green, 2005). Experiential learning, in all of these forms, helps to address the gap between school-based knowledge and the knowledge required in the workplace (Kolb, 2014).

While there are many forms of experiential learning, such as apprenticeships, that are older than the modern school system itself, the major traditions of experiential learning popular today emerged as part of a revolution in educational theory and methods in the late-19th and 20th centuries (Kolb, 2014). These experiential learning movements challenged traditional forms of top-down, teacher-led classroom education. They instead promoted more learner-centered forms of education, where learners would participate in knowledge development through reflection on their own experience. By respecting the personal experience of the learner, experiential learning de-centers the “expert” and encourages dialogue between personal experience and theory or established knowledge. It emphasizes learning through dialogue between people and between different forms of knowledge. The constructive conflict that can emerge through this dialogue stimulates the development of new knowledge (Kolb, 2014). This is conducive to critical thinking and creativity. Experiential learning has been central to efforts to expand education access for people with different modes of learning, who may be less well-served by traditional education. It is particularly relevant to disadvantaged groups whose social environments condition them less for classroom or textbook modes of learning and instead encourage modes of learning sometimes characterized as “street wisdom” (Kolb, 2014). Experiential learning approaches have also been seen as important for responding to the fast-changing knowledge environment of modern society, where learners must become self-directed learners, continuously learning from their own experience (Kolb, 2014).

Kolb’s (2014) seminal experiential learning theory responds to critics who contend that experiential learning overemphasizes narrow personal experience, at the expense of the broader accumulation of knowledge contained in theory and academic knowledge. He explains the importance of experiential learning in the context of a broader theory of the learning process. In Kolb’s theory, concrete experience (CE), abstract conceptualization (AC), reflective observation (RO), and active experimentation (AE) are mutually reinforcing. Different learners have different dominant modes of grasping experience (CE or AC) and different dominant modes of acting on experiences (RO or AE), which form different Learning Styles. Rather than standing in opposition to abstract conceptualization, concrete experience is an equally important and complementary form of knowledge. It serves both as a source of abstract knowledge (through RO) and a testing ground for abstract knowledge (through AE). Kolb reconciles abstract conceptualization and concrete experience in a dialectical relationship. By doing so, he provides theoretical support for experiential learning and for integrating it with classroom learning. He also explains the importance of varied approaches to education that cater to different learning styles, with experiential learning constituting an important component of diverse learning approaches.

2.2 Learning outside the classroom

Experiential learning often, but not always, takes place outside the classroom. A separate literature on Learning Outside the Classroom (LOC) highlights the value that alternative settings can have for student learning. LOC can be defined as teaching and learning that takes place outside the formal classroom context (Malone, 2008; Parr, 2020). It includes a wide range of learning experiences in both indoor and outdoor settings. These can include museums, galleries, science centers, playgrounds, the wilderness, and of course workplaces (Malone, 2008). Eschach (2007) distinguishes structured forms of LOC from spontaneous, unstructured forms of learning that happen in everyday life. He refers to the former as “non-formal learning” as opposed to spontaneous “informal learning.” Today, non-formal learning that involves structured or semi-structured activities outside of the classroom is often promoted by educators

and education policymakers as a complement to classroom learning. Initiatives to promote learning outside of the classroom include the efforts of the Council for Learning Outside the Classroom in the UK and the *udeskole* movement in Norway (Bolling et al., 2018).

LOC has been advocated as a means of providing students with new, exciting, and challenging experiences to aid their learning. It has been associated with a broad range of benefits, including improvements in learning motivation, learning outcomes, interpersonal skills, problem-solving and critical-thinking ability, and even mental and physical health (Malone, 2008). Eschach (2007) groups the effects of LOC into cognitive and affective aspects. Affective aspects include self-efficacy, motivation, and interest or attitude towards a topic of learning, while cognitive aspects include knowledge and thinking skills. Malone (2008), through a broad survey of the literature, identifies a more extensive set of effects. She notes that LOC can benefit students in cognitive, personal, social, emotional, and physical dimensions. The cognitive dimension includes exposure to new knowledge that might not be found in the classroom and improved critical thinking and problem-solving skills that can come from engaged experiences. The personal dimension covers changes in attitudes and values, overlapping with Eschach's affective aspect. This may include the stronger sense of social or environmental responsibility that can come with experiences in nature or the community. The social dimension includes the development of relationships and interpersonal skills through the social interactions LOC encourages. The emotional and physical dimensions include various benefits to mental and physical health. This might take place through the therapeutic effects of natural environments or the opportunities for physical activity that LOC can provide (Malone, 2008).

While some have questioned the value of LOC, there are now many studies demonstrating the positive effects of well-designed LOC for learning (Eschach, 2007; Malone, 2008). The affective or personal effects of LOC are well-demonstrated. For example, a variety of studies demonstrate the ability of out-of-classroom activities such as museum or science center visits to foster student enthusiasm for science learning and positive attitudes towards science (Finson & Enochs, 1987; Ramey-Gassert, 1997). Although studies of the effectiveness of LOC for enhancing cognitive learning outcomes are more mixed, studies have also demonstrated that out-of-school learning can enhance student achievement, as reflected in test scores (Cheong & Swee, 1987; SEER, 2005). Furthermore, LOC has been shown to stimulate critical thinking skills (Malone, 2008). Scholars note that LOC is more likely to have positive cognitive effects when it is well-linked to and complements formal classroom learning (Cheong & Swee, 1987; Eschach, 2007). In terms of social effects, in a study of a class of Danish students who spent one day a week learning in a forest, Mygind (2009) found that the out-of-classroom environment expanded children's friendship circles while also promoting more positive social interactions among students. In a large-scale study of American summer camp participants, Thurber et al. (2007) have also found that these out of school learning experiences have positive effects for the social skills and emotional health of children. The qualitative difference in the way students learn in out of classroom settings is important to note. Out-of-classroom learning has been found to stimulate more inquisitive and exploratory mindsets and more student-centered learning that strengthens different competencies than classroom education (Bolling et al., 2018).

3 Method: Case study

Case study research is typically used for the exploration of *how* or *why* questions (Yin, 2009). It aims to produce comprehensive accounts of a process that allow for in-depth analysis. Case study research is particularly relevant in cases where complex contextual conditions are important and the boundaries between the phenomenon being investigated and its context are not clear-cut (Yin, 2009). The use of diverse sources of evidence to triangulate information and

produce comprehensive understanding is stressed in the case study method (Yin, 2006). Rather than seeking generalized insight based on large samples, case study research pursues generalizable insight through logical inference based on thick understanding. Case studies may be approached through pre-existing theoretical lenses, but are also valuable for allowing new insights and explanations to emerge from in-depth knowledge of the case itself (Yin, 2006).

The present study is based upon CLAP-TECH's pioneering project to develop a new alternative education pathway in Hong Kong. It adopts a case study approach in order to reconstruct how the bootcamp, as a learning activity outside the classroom within the CLAP-TECH Multimedia Storytelling curriculum, contributed to student learning. As coordinators of the Multimedia Storytelling program, the research team has comprehensive understanding of the planning and implementation of the case. Observation and a post-event survey were adopted to understand the results of the bootcamp. Specifically, an anonymous post-event survey containing 24 questions was conducted with students on the final day of the bootcamp. The survey questions covered four areas: (1) bootcamp learning environment (3 questions); (2) bootcamp content (10 questions); (3) bootcamp learning and personal development (11 questions); and (4) open-ended questions reflecting on the bootcamp (2 questions). A total of 62 students completed the post-event survey. Observations were collected verbally from teachers in daily lunch debriefings and in a debriefing after the bootcamp.

4 Overview of the case study: The Innovation Bootcamp

The CLAP-TECH Multimedia Storytelling Innovation Bootcamp was held at M21, a media studio with facilities for multimedia training and production managed by the Hong Kong Federation of Youth. M21 focuses on serving youth and providing training, resources, and interactive space to support the development and expression of their creativity. The approximately 4000 square meter space features a variety of facilities for media production, including a recording studio, band room, audio room, computer room, theatre, make-up room, classrooms, and multi-functional spaces for filming and recording. M21 trainers provided facilities, programming, and trainers for the bootcamp. The cost of the bootcamp amounted to roughly 3800 HKD per student. Staff invested approximately 23 person-days of time in preparing for the camp.

The main learning objectives of the bootcamp were to identify the entire media production process, to learn about the different roles in the production process, and to develop collaborative working skills. The bootcamp was designed in line with Kolb's experiential learning theory, asking students to engage in hands-on practice and then learn through reflection on their experiences. It adopted a project-based model of learning, challenging students to work in groups to produce self-directed short videos. A central component of the bootcamp design was group work. The 82 students were divided into 16 work groups of roughly five students each, producing one collaborative project per group. Groups mixed students from different schools based on a pre-camp survey of students' interests and role preferences, such as whether they preferred to shoot with a professional camera or mobile phone, and whether they wished to act, direct or play a supporting role. The sixteen groups were supported by M21 tutors who were generally university students with media or training production experience. In addition to the M21 tutors, teachers from students' secondary schools provided conflict mediation support. The group set-up encouraged students to meet and work with new people.

The content of the bootcamp included lectures and workshops introducing basic shooting, editing, and post-production skills, alternating with self-guided practice. Table 1 summarizes the daily schedule of the bootcamp. Over the course of the three days (7 hours per day), students experienced the full production cycle of a short video. They brainstormed ideas, created storylines, acted out and shot their ideas, and finally edited their footage and added post-production effects. On the first day, hands-on learning activities introduced students to basic

skills including Studio Filming, Live Broadcasting, Chroma Key Studio Technique, and Podcast and Voice-Over Production. Students participated in a sharing by a key opinion leader (KOL) on content creation. In the afternoon and over the next two days, students began the process of producing their own short videos. Additional workshops guided them along the way in ideation, story writing, shooting, and video editing. The students' work resulted in 2-minute original short videos. On the final day, a representative from each group presented the final product, screening their video and sharing the group's story concept. Table 2 lists the titles of students' final products. A vote was then held to choose the winners of three awards—"Best Film," "Best Female Actor," and "Best Male Actor." One group was selected for each of the three award categories and each of the students matching the award category within the group were given an award (e.g. all female actors in the group awarded Best Female Actor). All students, M21 instructors, secondary school teachers, and CLAP-TECH staff participated in the vote. Given the occurrence of a significant group conflict during the bootcamp process and students' successful resolution of the conflict, instructors decided to provide a special award to this group for their conflict resolution skills.

Abstract conceptualization and experimentation were built-in throughout the bootcamp learning experience. Experimentation to test out abstract concepts through concrete experience was a critical part of the learning process. On each day of the camp, the relevant skills to be practiced during the day were first introduced. Students were then advised to experiment with the new ideas or different shooting styles they had learned. After transforming abstract concepts into concrete experience through their experimentation during the day, students were required to reflect on their experiences through the idea sharing, debriefing, and presentation sessions at the end of each day. During the learning process, instructors encouraged students to reflect on the concepts behind their content creation and relate these concepts with what they had learned from the first module of the Multimedia Storytelling curriculum—Overview of Multimedia Storytelling. This facilitated the use of concrete experience to deepen abstract conceptualization. The evaluation survey carried out on the final day also allowed students to reflect on their learning experiences and share their thoughts on how the bootcamp experience could be improved in the future.

Table 1
Multimedia Storytelling Innovation Bootcamp Schedule

Time	Content	CLAP-TECH Pathway Essential Attributes
Day 1		
10:00-10:30	Opening ceremony	Motivation
10:30-12:30	A taste of the media world: hands-on experience workshops	Analytical Thinking Curiosity
13:30-16:00	Content creation Key-Opinion Leader (KOL) sharing	Analytical Thinking Communication
16:20-17:20	Group discussion of ideas	Collaboration Communication
17:20-18:00	Idea sharing	Communication Curiosity
Day 2		
09:00-10:30	Basics of video shooting (lecture)	Analytical Thinking Curiosity
10:30-12:30	Video shooting practice	Curiosity Self-management
13:30-17:20	Video shooting	Collaboration Integrity

		Leadership Resilience Responsibility Self-management
17:20-18:00	Debriefing	
Day 3		
09:00-10:30	Video editing workshop	Analytical Thinking Curiosity Self-management
10:30-12:30	Video editing session	Collaboration Integrity Leadership Resilience Responsibility Self-management
13:30-15:00	Final touch up & presentation preparation	Collaboration Communication Leadership Resilience Responsibility
15:30-18:00	Premiere, presentation & closing ceremony	Communication Integrity Motivation

Table 2
Titles of Student Group Videos

Group	Video
1	If I Were Dead
2	Water-Level Person
3	Loss of Ability
4	Chaotic World
5	Friends who Cherish One Another
6	Heart Break
7	What's Wrong with Xiaoming
8	Friendship
9	Copying Homework
10	E——Love
11	Running in Two Directions
12	Mirror vs BTS pop singers team
13	Lesson
14	What a Coincidence to Run Into You
15	Young Love and Sickness Story – Go-Miracle
16	Tomato Wars

5 Evaluation and findings

The intensive project-based learning of the Innovation Bootcamp spurred student personal, cognitive, and social development. For many students, it served as their first contact with the actual video production process. Due to the influence of COVID-19 for the duration of the Multimedia Storytelling course thus far, it was also the first time many students had been able to work in a group on any form of hands-on learning. Instructors noted that this had a notable effect on student enthusiasm and commitment that was noticeable in later coursework and activities. However, a number of challenges also affected the bootcamp results. The

achievements and challenges of the bootcamp were reflected both in observations from school teachers and M21 instructors and in student post-event survey responses.

In debriefing sessions during and after the bootcamp, teachers' most prominent observations concerned students' quality of collaboration during the bootcamp. The problems they noted included language barriers (some students were only competent in English or Putonghua) that had impeded collaboration in some groups. They also suggested that students might be more engaged if they were in teams with others from the same school and that keeping students from one school in the same group would make it easier for teachers to mediate conflicts. On the other hand, teachers noted many positive social results that resulted from the collaborative set-up of the bootcamp, including that students had made friends from other schools, that some inactive students were able to collaborate and felt motivated, and that students had learned how to resolve conflicts. With regard to facilitating cognitive learning, instructors suggested that allowing more time for students to debrief their final products, after completing their videos and before their presentations, would allow students to better process their learning experience and enhance project evaluation. Instructors also suggested training in presentation skills would help to present their insights about the video production process in a more logical way.

In the post-event survey for student feedback, with the exception of two open ended questions, the other 15 questions asked students to rate their experience or agreement with various statements on a five-point scale. Tables 3 and 4 summarize the learning outcome, activity, and logistics survey results. Students rated the Innovation Bootcamp highly in terms of personal development outcomes such as interest and confidence in goal setting, cognitive outcomes such as creativity and problem-solving skills, and social outcomes such as collaboration with groupmates and confidence in group work. Among the different activities, hands-on, engaged experiences including both the hands-on skills workshops and production process activities were generally rated more highly than the small number of less hands-on activities. In general, students also appreciated the M21 facilities where the boot camp was held, although some found the location and timing inconvenient.

On questions concerning personal outcomes of the bootcamp, most students agreed or strongly agreed that the bootcamp had been interesting, that they had been exposed to new experiences through the bootcamp, and that they felt more confident in setting future learning goals after the bootcamp. Slightly fewer reported that they found the KOL sharing inspiring. In addition, in the open-ended comments on their overall experience of the bootcamp, many students expressed that the bootcamp had been fun. Others indicated that they had had new experiences and that the bootcamp was exciting. One student commented that the bootcamp took a lot of time and effort but that s/he was very satisfied with the final result. Overall, survey results indicate that the bootcamp experience spurred student interest and that it gave them a stronger sense of their goals in future study.

Table 3
Summary Post-event Student Survey Learning Outcomes

Dimension	Statement	% Agree/ Strongly Agree	Mean*	SD
Personal	The activities of the bootcamp are interesting.	79.0	4.16	0.79
	The Key Opinion Leader' sharing is inspiring.	66.2	3.95	0.88
	The bootcamp enriches my exposure.	77.5	4.23	0.80
	I feel more confident to set goals for my further study.	75.8	4.19	0.81
Cognitive	The activities of the bootcamp develop my creativity.	72.5	4.15	0.87
	The activities of the bootcamp enhance my problem-solving skills.	72.5	4.15	0.87

	After the bootcamp, I have a deeper understanding of the Multimedia Storytelling ApL course.	74.2	4.15	0.85
	The bootcamp equip me with the skills and knowledge to study in the Multimedia Storytelling ApL course.	77.4	4.21	0.79
Social	I found a clear role in my group.	75.8	4.16	0.91
	I collaborate well with my groupmates in the bootcamp.	71.0	4.16	0.99
	I feel more confident to work with others in groups to complete the assigned task.	72.6	4.16	0.87

* Five-point scale

The rate of positive responses for cognitive results was slightly lower than for personal outcomes, although also generally positive. A majority of students agreed or strongly agreed that the bootcamp had enhanced their creativity, problem-solving skills, and understanding of the Multimedia Storytelling course content. In particular, a high percentage of students agreed that the bootcamp had helped equipped them with skills and knowledge to study in the Multimedia Storytelling ApL course. In their open-ended comments, a number of students commented that they had learned a lot.

Survey results concerning social interaction and social skills were mixed, with many very positive responses but also some negative responses, likely due to one group's difficult collaboration experience during the bootcamp. While 75.8% agreed or strongly agreed that they found a clear role in their group, 4.8% also disagreed. A majority of students indicated strong agreement that they had collaborated well with their groupmates—the highest rate of strong agreement among the survey questions, but another 6.5% disagreed. There was more general agreement, however, that the bootcamp experience had enhanced confidence in working with others, with only 1.6% of students indicating disagreement. This suggests that even those who had had negative collaboration experiences experienced growth in collaboration skills as a result. The negative results concerning groupwork in the evaluation survey seem likely to be due to one group's conflict on the first day of the bootcamp over choosing a topic for their film. While students conflicted sharply the first day, over the course of the bootcamp, and with the mediation of the M21 instructors and school teachers, they resolved the conflict and were able to produce a satisfactory final product. These difficult collaboration experiences nevertheless enhanced student learning.

In open-ended commentary, many students commented on their collaborative experience. One expressed being thankful to be able to produce a great product in collaboration with others; another reflected that the capacity of one person is limited and teamwork is key. One student commented on making new friends. At the same time, there were several comments suggesting that collaboration experiences for certain students could have been better. This included one student who indicated "I wish we had better communication," another who commented poor collaboration affected the quality of their work, and a third who expressed that they wished to be able to choose their own groups. In terms of social skills development, for the majority of students, collaboration experiences appear to have been a highlight of the bootcamp. Meanwhile, even for those who experienced challenges, the chance to resolve and work through conflict was a learning experience.

Table 4

Summary of Post-event Student Survey Activity and Logistics Ratings

Dimension	Component	% Good/ Very Good	Mean*	SD
Activities	Hands-on experience	79.0	4.21	0.77

	Content creation	77.4	4.19	0.83
	KOL sharing	64.6	3.94	0.88
	Group discussion	74.2	4.19	0.99
	Sharing	75.8	4.16	0.83
	Shooting	80.7	4.27	0.81
	Editing	79.0	4.31	0.80
	Post-production	79.1	4.24	0.78
	Presentation	69.3	4.06	0.86
Logistics	Location convenience	38.7	3.26	1.16
	Facilities	82.2	4.26	0.75
	Overall time arrangement of the bootcamp	67.7	3.84	0.94

* Five-point scale

With regard to specific components of the bootcamp, Table 4 summarizes students' ratings of the different activities. Shooting, editing, and post-production were rated most highly among the activities. Ratings of the hands-on experience workshops, content creation, and group discussion were also high. Group discussion showed more variation and more negative responses, in line with the collaboration difficulties observed in a small number of groups. The KOL sharing and student presentations were slightly less popular. The lower rating for presentations may reflect the difficulties students experienced in presentation, as observed by the teachers. In general, students seemed to enjoy hands-on experiences the most.

Finally, in terms of the venue and logistics of the bootcamp, students were generally enthusiastic about the M21 facilities, but less satisfied with its location and with the time arrangements. As the bootcamp was a day camp, requiring students to commute back and forth each of the three days, students arriving late in the morning posed a challenge for camp logistics. In their open-ended commentary, students also expressed that it was difficult to get up so early in the morning and that the venue was far from their homes.

Overall, both students and teachers saw the bootcamp as having a positive impact on students' personal and social development. The bootcamp enhanced student interest and motivation, while helping them learn to collaborate with others. Its impacts for cognitive skills such as creativity, problem-solving, and enhancement of course related skills and knowledge were also assessed positively, although less prominently so. Teachers indicated room for enhancement by better preparing students for presentations and giving them more time to process their new experiences in a final debriefing session.

6 Discussion and Conclusion

The Innovation Bootcamp served as the first opportunity for the Multimedia Storytelling Applied Learning Course students to craft a complete piece of work under a tight deadline. It provided a project-based experimental learning opportunity outside the classroom that allowed students to engage in self-directed, collaborative learning. Students exercised their creativity and mimicked the real work process in the course of creating an original short video. The groupwork setting required students to work with unfamiliar people, developing communication and collaboration skills in the process. The out-of-classroom setting of the camp stimulated student interest and allowed for different modes of interaction than would usually happen in the classroom. Student feedback and teacher observation from the bootcamp corroborate that intensive experiential learning in an out-of-classroom setting has a positive impact on students' personal development, spurring their interest and motivation to learn. It also challenges them to develop social skills that are increasingly important in new collar jobs and fosters cognitive skills including creativity and problem-solving ability. At the same time, the camp served as an opportunity for instructors to identify talent among students. One

prominent remaining challenge was students' reluctance to engage in written work such as writing reflections and their lack of preparation for presentations. More training in writing and presentation skills could be incorporated into the regular curriculum to better prepare students for future bootcamps.

Based on the positive experiences of the Innovation Bootcamp, it is recommended that mini bootcamps involving intensive project-based learning experiences be included as a future part of vocational and professional education for young people. Ensuring the quality of the group collaboration experience is important for making the most of the learning experience. Instructors and program managers should pay attention to how to arrange groupings of students to facilitate communication and to putting in place conflict resolution mechanisms. With attention to these factors, bootcamp learning experiences can be a valuable model of experiential learning to foster the creativity, problem-solving, and team work skills young people will need in the world of work.

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